

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: The John Muir Trust

Identifying Wild Places using Social
and Physical Datasets

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Wild places can be found across the United Kingdom. These may be remote mountains in the Scottish Highlands, windswept cliffs on the Northern Ireland coast, woody glades across Wales or overgrown parks and cemeteries in England's cities. Much of where these wild places are found depends on the definition of what it means to be a wild place. Recent studies have given evidence that wild places are vital to ensuring biodiversity and robust ecologies, as well as having a direct influence on mental and physical health [1, 2, 3]. In this challenge, we combine qualitative survey data with geospatial datasets to better understand the public's perception of wild places, their distribution across the UK, and possible measures to evaluate what makes a wild place be considered wild. The project overview is given in Figure 1.

This work was led by the John Muir Trust (JMT), a Scottish charitable organisation dedicated to the conservation of wild places and wilderness in the UK. Through its work, the trust aims to foster a greater appreciation for the intrinsic value of wilderness. It collaborates with local communities,

Figure 1: Outline of both objectives and steps undertaken in this project.

policymakers, and other organisations to advocate for responsible land use and the protection of the UK's remaining wild spaces. The trust aspires to ensure that future generations have the opportunity to experience and benefit from unspoiled natural environments.

1.2 Main objectives

To better understand what it means for a place to be considered as wild and where these places can be found, we combined qualitative (social-based) and quantitative (physical-based) data. This data motivates the following objectives:

1. Understanding the role of different metrics for choosing wild places and how these relate to objective attributes derived from physical environment datasets.
2. Explore any potential differences between how wild places are perceived between different population groups.
3. Comparing how the public chooses their favourite “local wild places” and “national wild places”.
4. Identifying the top regions and locations that the public perceive to contain wild places.
5. Construct a ‘wild place index’ (WPI) that quantifies attributes and could be used to identify regions in terms of their potential ‘wildness’.

1.3 Approach

We used a combination of social and geophysical data to better understand the connection between wild places in the UK and the public. Social data was gathered from two surveys, collected by Survation and directly from JMT. For both cohorts, the survey contained the same set of questions, asking participants to choose their favourite local and national wild place and asked for information on the attributes that contributed to their choice. Geospatial data was collected using open source datasets covering features such as population density, community involvement, and accessibility.

In this work, we used a combination of statistical analysis, text and natural language processing, clustering algorithms, geospatial analysis and classical machine learning methods such as linear regression, random forest classification and XGBoost.

1.4 Main conclusions

This work considered the role and understanding of wild places in the UK, as understood through public survey data and geospatial data. We make the following conclusions:

- The public conception of wild places is multi-faceted where the most popular attributes of wild places in the UK included “scenery, quiet, health, nature”. We also found evidence that choices of a favourite wild place is at least partly driven by personal reasons such as past memories and experiences.
- We observed that demographic factors can influence how the public report on their perception of wild places, such as age, and type of dwelling.
- The majority of national wild places chosen were concentrated within 20 clusters across the UK. Local wild places were significantly more dispersed. We were able to label these regions in an unsupervised way using clustering and geospatial data.
- There were differences in the qualities attributed to wild places from survey data to those quantified using external datasets. Specifically, we found that survey participants would rank wild places highly based on *scenery* and *presence of people*, despite this not being supported by the external datasets. On the other hand, *activities* and *sights and sounds of nature* were relatively well aligned.
- We constructed a Wild Place Index (WPI) using both survey and physical datasets. We were able to predict a wildness score for regions that had no social data using the physical datasets with 70% accuracy as well as identifying what attribute is likely to be most important for this region with 90% accuracy.

1.5 Limitations

As with any time limited investigation, one of the main restriction for this work was time. Specifically, the datasets (both social and physical) gave many initial results that could be pursued in future work. All work was partly truncated to ensure early results were completed and made presentable within the allocated time. This meant that clear analyses were favoured over more comprehensive analyses. More broadly, the subjective concept of wild places meant that geospatial data were difficult to compare to survey data. Additional discussion of data quality issues are described in Section 2.

1.6 Recommendations and Future Work

This work provides preliminary evidence on relating social datasets to physical datasets in the context of quantifying wild places in the UK. Future work might explore other datasets such as image or satellite data. This might follow the the approach taken in [4], where a deep learning model was used for object recognition, first trained on satellite images with labelled information. However, this relies on the suitability of both external datasets and the social datasets. Given this, more discussion and research would be needed to establish how external datasets overlap with the public's perception of wildness.

To understand the impact of using external datasets on wild place scores, we performed statistical tests on features important for identifying wild places, using external data and survey data grouped by demographics. However, due to time constraints, we were only able to perform this analysis based on age. These results were insufficient to explain the whole story of how external data impacts feature importance. More investigations are needed in the future, such as comparisons to other characteristics or by using principle features analysis (PFA) [5], which combines K-means clustering and statistical testing. The most important features could then be selected by inspecting the most influential principal features.

We were also not able to conduct a systematic assessment of all clustering parameters across the methods used. An important avenue for future work would be to assess the impact of varying these parameters.

We expect that it would be straightforward to identify hierarchical clustering parameters that would produce clusters with a desired average/maximum size. Once parameter tuning has been carried out for each approach individually, it would then be necessary to perform a systematic comparison across the different approaches in order to determine which best captures favourite wild places at a given resolution. However, determining the “best” set of parameters requires careful consideration about the desired characteristics of the final set of clusters.

We constructed a Wild Place Index (WPI) that translated the wildness score to a gridded representation of the UK. We only performed preliminary and qualitative comparison between the WPI and the JMT cohort’s favourite wild place in the UK as the sample size was larger. Future work should look to expand this to both cohorts, both national and local favourite wild place, and perform a quantitative analysis between social scores and the WPI.

When determining the weights for the WPI, we also only considered the JMT survey cohort. It would be interesting to extend this analysis to the Survation cohort and investigate differences in what features that are important to distinguishing a local and national wild place. Further work is required to verify the accuracy of these weights. For example, we found that accessibility is more important in local than in UK wild places for the majority of survey respondents. Yet, this weighting would give a higher score to national park than a local city park. This indicates that the weighting for a WPI might have to be conditional on the ‘type’ or ‘aspect’ of a wild place of interest.

We note that the WPI can be used in the future to potentially help identify the wildness of newly discovered locations (provided there is data from the eight external datasets at this location). To properly vet the wildness index, a dataset should be created of both wild and non-wild places. Locations that are wild should score much higher than locations that are not. Once further confidence is given to the WPI and the dataset used to construct this, more methods can be trialled to predict new wild places such as graph-based approaches.

Finally, we have identified the top 20 wild places using our unsupervised approach for wild places chosen as national favourites by the JMT survey

cohort. Future work should look at applying this approach to both the Survation cohort and favoured local wild places.

2 Data overview

The primary data provided by JMT is a combination of social and physical data. This survey data was collected in two parts: (1) a national social media campaign run by the JMT to attract as many responses as possible and (2) a demographically and geographically representative sample of 2,000 UK adults. Supplementary physical-based data includes publicly available geospatial datasets provided by government bodies, and freely available from the Ordnance Survey (OS). These include 42 mapped Scottish Wild Land Areas produced by Nature.Scot and UK greenspaces, produced by OS. Geospatial datasets were provided in vector shapefile format, or other geospatial format such as .kml or geodatabase.

2.1 Dataset description

The “Wild Places Survey” was developed by the John Muir Trust. Questions and question options were chosen by JMT based on the output of a Diverse Voices workshop run with Dialogue Matters, which engaged people from all four UK nations of differing gender, age, ethnicity, sexual orientation and disability. The survey data consists of selected chosen “Wild Places” as points (latitude, longitude) and reasoning as to why this place was selected, in the form of select-one, select-multiple, free text and Likert-scale questions. In total, there were 9,800 records of respondents collected through a social-media campaign conducted by the John Muir Trust and 2,100 records collected by Survation polling company.

In total, nineteen characteristics of wild places were provided for respondents in the survey, with full descriptions provided in Appendix A. The shorthand reference for these options are:

- Access
- Adventure
- Communities
- Activities
- Air-Water
- Health

- History
- Land Management
- Light
- Absence of litter
- Man-made
- Structures
- Nature
- Paths
- Quiet
- Remoteness
- Scenery
- Science
- Weather
- Wildlife

There was also a free text prompt for participants to provide any additional reasons for selecting their local and UK-wide wild places. Though broad, the survey was non-exhaustive in capturing the factors that a participant may consider in evaluating wild places; the free text prompt allows for other factors to be at least partially considered.

Unfortunately, as this prompt was not mandatory, not all participants provided an answer. Only 56 out of 2,100 participants in the Survation survey provided an answer for their favourite local wild place. 646 out of 9,800 participants provided a free-text answer for their favourite local wild place in the JMT survey. Similarly, only 75 and 497 participants answered for their favourite UK-wide wild place for the Survation and JMT surveys respectively. As such, these data have only limited explanatory or predictive power for exploring the qualities of wild places in the UK.

Alongside the information about wild places, respondents were able to provide (optional) information on demographic characteristics of age; gender, ethnicity, health conditions, and type of dwelling.

Geospatial datasets were used in this project for three main objectives:

1. Labelling wild place clusters with place names using existing landscape classifications such as National Parks, Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONBs) and Nature Reserves. This allows for the each wild place to have a name in the wild places register, rather than just an ID.
2. Labelling clusters use pre-digitised areas (polygons) for geospatial analysis of physical data, rather than point data alone. This is beneficial as a point sample of an attribute might not be representative of the larger area such as a National Parks.

3. To augment the survey data with additional physical data about each chosen wild place, to further inform the criteria for answering the question “What makes a wild place a wild place?” and as input to a “wildness index” model which was used to predict unlabelled wild places across the UK.

In order to relate the social data (comprising survey data described above) with external quantitative information, we used several sources for physical geospatial data. These included Globio4 (2015), OS Built Up Area dataset, LandScan Glob dataset, Registered charity numbers for each county in the four countries in the UK, 21 heritage lists and the OS Road Networks. Further information on these datasets are provided in Section 6 and in Appendix C.

2.2 Data preprocessing and quality issues

The survey data was preprocessed prior to the Data Study Group (DSG), with the following steps undertaken:

- Data collected by surveying company Survation were pre-processed by them. Survation shared that they took the following steps in their pre-processing: *Data were weighted to the profile of all adults in the UK aged 18+. Data were weighted by age, gender and region. Targets for these weighted data were derived from Office for National Statistics Data.*
- Data collected by the John Muir Trust underwent data quality checks and cleaning: All personal information was stripped from the dataset. Survey responses suspected of speeding (those who completed the survey in less than two minutes) and straight-lining were removed.
- Geospatial output from survey data underwent the following post-processing: Responses where a map pin had not been moved from the default position (c. 5%) were geo-coded using Google Maps API with the user input place name and then manually checked that they were within the named place. Any places that could not be geo-located, or identified beyond reasonable doubt (e.g. place name was ambiguous, or had multiple results), were removed from the dataset (<1% of the dataset). Given a small proportion of respondents failed

to move the interactive map, we believe that the majority were able to use this technology to some degree.

- Large geospatial datasets such as the OS Terrain50 dataset, were stitched together from tiles, into a virtual raster, so that processing could take place over the whole dataset.

Following preprocessing, several issues with the data remained:

- A small percentage of survey responses (<1%) suspected of speeding or straight-lining remain, as both survey completions were incentivised by both JMT and Survation
- Around 5% survey respondents failed to move the interactive map before selecting a favourite wild place.
- Spelling errors persisted in “Place Names”
- It is noted that the interactive map element of the survey may have put off some respondents, due to not being able to correctly read the map, use the technology, or locate their favourite wild place.
- The total number of free-text responses was small, restricting the value of using text analysis and that the bias inherent to survey data gathered from the JMT campaign was difficult to explicitly identify.

It was not expected that these issues were significant, given that they represented a small proportion of the output data. Spelling errors were easily amended.

3 Exploratory Data Analysis

In order to better understand why the public indicated specific locations as their favourite wild places, data analysis was undertaken to see how the characteristics varied across survey cohort, local and national location, and demographics within a survey. This analysis gave insight into how the characteristics of people relate to what makes a wild place special for them.

Key Findings

1. All characteristics of wild places were referenced by participants, indicating that the suggested list was relevant to how the public perceive wild places. However, text analysis highlighted personal and sentimental reasons for choosing a place.
2. The mentioning of the characteristics of wild places was not equal. There are some that are mentioned more frequently such as *Scenery*, *Quiet*, *Nature*, *Health*, and *Wildlife*, and some that were less frequent such as *Light*, *Science*, *Activities*, and *History*.
3. Two demographics had interesting variation in which categories were attributed to wild places; age and how urban the respondent's home location is.
4. We identified key differences between the Survation cohort and JMT cohort. *Weather* and *Adventure* were all chosen more frequently as being significant to why a wild place was special for the JMT cohort than for the Survation cohort. However, *Access* and *Paths* were much higher for the Survation cohort, as the wider public may value good accessibility.
5. Semantic clustering was used to group locations based on more personal measures for why a location was chosen. These include locations with "fond memories" such as an engagement or those used for walks. However, the cluster label can also be incorrectly specified, depend on the natural language model used, and will likely require checks to ensure cluster labels are sensible.

3.1 Differences between Survation and JMT survey respondents

Although the two surveys asked the same questions, the results were significantly different due to the research design. The Survation survey was conducted by a specialist survey company (Survation) and ensured that the respondents were representative of the UK population. Survation attempted to minimise non-response bias from the survey by selecting respondents themselves. The JMT survey had more respondents but

these self-selected by clicking through a link shared on the JMT social media pages. Given this, the two surveys gathered data with samples that are representative of two different populations. The Survation survey was designed to be broadly representative of the UK population. On the other hand, the JMT survey was expected to represent people more interested in outdoor and wild places and who were more likely to be aware of JMT's social media pages. Efforts were made to minimise this by JMT, by using external marketing partners who designed the visuals and text to appeal to a wider audience (this included analysis of the social media engagement data and targeting under-represented groups as the marketing campaign went on). Admittedly, there will still have been far more engagement by those who would usually interact with JMT anyway (e.g. we saw much higher proportion of responses from Scotland), but this was definitely minimised by the marketing team.

When considering the demographic data between the two groups, we found that the JMT cohort had a high representation of female respondents, were more likely to identify as ethnically white, were more likely to be young and were less likely to live in urban dwellings than those from in the Survation cohort. On the other hand, we found that the Survation cohort had a higher proportion of non-white respondents and were more likely to live in an urban city than rural settlement. Demographic data is shown in tables Table 2 and further figures and discussion is included in Appendix B.

Despite the differences in the selection process for the two survey cohorts, the distribution of attributes were broadly similar. Both cohorts found that *Scenery* and *Quiet* were most important. Of the 19 attributes used in this analysis, all were relevant to both cohorts for why a wild place was important to a respondent. This is shown in Table 3 below.

However, there were also key differences between the two cohorts. For example, *Weather* and *Adventure* were more frequently chosen by the JMT cohort than the Survation cohort. This supports the view that the JMT were more likely to be outdoor enthusiasts who enjoyed being outdoors (weather permitting). On the other hand, *Access* and *Paths* were higher for the Survation cohort. This indicates that some of the most popular wild place for the wider public still requires good accessibility.

Characteristic	JMT Cohort	Survation Cohort
<i>Age Group</i>		
Over 60	10.8%	33.1%
41 - 60	38.0%	35.5%
26 - 40	38.3%	24.8%
18 - 25	12.3%	6.5%
Under 18	0.3%	0.0%
Prefer not to answer	0.2%	0.1%
<i>Gender</i>		
Female	61.1%	48.3%
Male	36.9%	51.3%
Diverse	0.11%	0.4%
Prefer not to answer	0.9%	0.2%
<i>Ethnicity</i>		
White	94.1%	88.6%
Asian or Asian British	0.8%	4.4%
Black, African, Caribbean or BI	0.2%	2.7%
Arab or other Middle Eastern ethnicity	0.1%	0.3%
Mixed or multiple ethnic groups	1.7%	2.4%
Other	0.9%	0.8%
Prefer not to answer	2.2%	0.9%
<i>Disability</i>		
Yes	23.7%	29.1%
No	72.8%	69.6%
Prefer not to answer	3.5%	1.3%
<i>Location</i>		
Urban, city	25.1%	27.6%
Urban, town	33.3%	45.3%
Rural, village	29.3%	20.6%
Rural, hamlet	5.7%	2.8%
Rural, non-settlement	4.1%	1.5%
None of the above	2.1%	1.8%
Prefer not to answer	0.4%	0.4%

Table 2: Breakdown of the demographic data for participants undertaking the JMT survey on wild places for both the Survation cohort and the JMT cohort.

	Proportion (Survation)	Proportion (JMT)
Scenery	11.9%	9.5%
Quiet	9.9%	8.5%
Nature	8.2%	6.6%
Access	7.3%	5.1%
Health	7.2%	8.4%
Wildlife	6.4%	6.1%
Air/Water	5.5%	5.9%
Paths	5.5%	3.4%
Remoteness	4.9%	5.3%
Weather	4.7%	6.5%
Man-made Structures	4.4%	5.0%
Litter	4.2%	4.7%
Land management	3.4%	3.6%
Adventure	3.4%	5.7%
Communities	2.8%	2.6%
History	2.8%	2.4%
Activities	2.7%	3.2%
Light	2.6%	3.9%
Science	1.6%	3.0%
Other	0.5%	0.6%

Table 3: Proportion of different attributes assigned to favourite wild places for both Survation and JMT cohorts. Bold indicates trends discussed in the main text.

3.2 Differences between local & national favourite wild places

All respondents were asked to choose their local and national favourite wild place. In general, we found there were similar attributes of favourite local and national wild places chosen for both cohorts. The proportion of attributes for different favourite wild places provided by survey participants is given in Table 4.

However, there were also notable differences in the response to both local and national favourite wild places and between cohorts. We found

that both cohorts were more likely to choose *Scenery*, *Paths*, and *Access* as important for local rather than national wild places and *Adventure* as more important for national than local. We observed that *Light* as more important for national wild places for the JMT cohort but broadly similar for the Survation cohort. However, the Survation cohort would more frequently choose *Weather* and *Health* as important for their national wild place and *Nature* as more important for their local wild place, though these attributes were broadly similar for the JMT cohort.

Here, we see that national wild places may be more likely to reflect adventurous activities, whereas local places require accessibility even when considered 'wild'. Additionally, some of the distinctions between cohorts reflect plausibly intuitive differences between the two demographics. For example, *Weather* and *Health* may be less important to the JMT cohort who were broadly younger and more likely to be outdoor enthusiasts. Other aspects are less intuitive, such as *Light* which doesn't as clearly reflect demographic differences between the two cohorts. However, statistical tests were not undertaken to quantify the significance of these findings and further work is required before drawing conclusions.

We next were interested to see if there was further information that could be gained from the distinction between local and national wild places, by quantifying the most frequent words given in the free-text response. Given the low sample size for the free words, we choose to aggregate both survey cohorts as we are interested in identifying new concepts for why a wild place might be special to a participant.

For the columns that are strings, we perform some initial preprocessing, including lemmatization and removal of redundant or common words. After preprocessing the data the most common words mentioned in the responses, as shown in Figure 2. For local responses in Figure 2a, we see some expected words like 'nature', 'hill', 'walk', as well as words associated with proximity such as 'local' and 'close'. An interesting observation from the national responses in Figure 2b is many of the words are sentimental such as 'family', 'love' and 'personal'.

(a) Local

(b) National

Figure 2: Common words of typed responses when asked: “What makes this wild place special?” for both local and national favourite wild places

Attribute	JMT		Survation	
	Local	National	Local	National
Scenery	11.9%	9.0%	11.9%	10.1%
Quiet	8.9%	7.9%	11.1%	9.3%
Nature	7.6%	6.1%	9.1%	7.3%
Health	6.9%	7.7%	7.5%	9.4%
Remoteness	6.4%	6.7%	3.0%	3.4%
Air Water	6.1%	6.5%	4.9%	5.2%
Wildlife	5.8%	5.7%	7.0%	6.6%
Access	5.7%	3.8%	9.2%	6.9%
Weather	5.1%	6.8%	4.1%	6.0%
Manmade Structures	4.5%	5.1%	4.3%	4.8%
Paths	4.4%	2.7%	6.9%	4.5%
Adventure	4.2%	6.8%	2.3%	4.3%
Litter	4.1%	4.7%	4.4%	4.8%
Land Management	3.8%	3.9%	2.9%	3.1%
Light	3.1%	4.6%	2.0%	2.9%
Communities	3.0%	2.7%	2.6%	2.5%
History	3.0%	2.2%	2.6%	2.6%
Activities	2.9%	3.6%	2.4%	2.7%
Science	2.0%	3.1%	1.1%	2.8%
Other	0.6%	0.5%	0.5%	0.8%

Table 4: Proportions of occurrences for each category in choosing a wild place for both national and local wild places and for both the JMT and Survation cohorts. Bold text denotes potential attributes of interest. Bold indicates trends discussed in the main text.

3.3 Characteristics mentioned by different demographic groups

Overall, we found that both surveys had representation across all five demographic characteristics that could be specified using the survey. However, we note that there were relatively few third gender and non-white ethnicity respondents, as well as under 18s in JMT survey, .

This can impact the significance of results for these categories and care should be taken when interpreting data from these categories. We chose not to include differences between ethnicities as there was a strong bias in the survey data. Future work should seek to gain further data on potential differences based on ethnicities. We also saw relatively little variation between genders and those with health conditions. Instead, we discuss only differences in age and settlement as these attributes had larger variation across both cohorts and for local and national favourite wild places.

Across different age groups, we saw interesting patterns whereby certain attributes would increase or decrease in their frequency of being chosen along with age. This is shown in Table 5. For example, we observed that *Adventure* would decrease in frequency with increasing age group for both national and local wild places and for both cohorts. On the other hand, *Nature* would increase with age for the favourite local wild place of the JMT cohort. *Wildlife* would increase in frequency with age for the Survation cohort whereas *Scenery* would decrease, though this was not observed for the JMT cohort.

For Settlements, we saw more variation. For example, we observed that both *Access* and *Remoteness* varying with settlement type for the favourite local wild place of the JMT cohort, where *Access* would decrease in frequency as settlements became less urbanised and *Remoteness* would increase. However, this was not observed for the favourite national place or at all for the Survation cohort. Additionally, both *Paths* and *Quiet* appeared to have a dependency on settlement, where *Paths* became less frequent with less urbanised settlements while *Quiet* became more frequent. One of the most striking observations was that *Light* (relating to light pollution) was very rarely chosen (1-2% of entries) for the favourite local wild place of both cohorts living in cities and increased dramatically in frequency as the respondents settlements became less urbanised.

As with the discussion above on broader differences between the two cohorts, no statistical tests were taken so we cannot comment on the statistical significance of these observations and recommend further work is undertaken to further verify these preliminary findings.

	under 18	18 - 25	26 - 40	41 - 60	over 60
JMT Local					
access	7.0%	6.3%	6.9%	6.9%	7.4%
adventure	7.4%	5.4%	4.8%	4.0%	3.0%
nature	5.7%	6.5%	7.0%	7.6%	7.8%
scenery	9.2%	10.5%	10.5%	9.8%	9.1%
wildlife	6.1%	5.9%	6.5%	6.9%	7.0%
JMT National					
access	4.5%	3.5%	3.4%	4.0%	4.6%
adventure	8.6%	7.6%	7.4%	6.2%	5.3%
nature	6.7%	5.7%	5.9%	6.3%	6.3%
scenery	8.6%	9.0%	9.2%	8.9%	8.6%
wildlife	5.1%	5.0%	5.5%	6.0%	6.1%
Survation Local					
access		7.1%	8.6%	9.0%	10.0%
adventure		4.4%	3.8%	2.2%	1.4%
nature		7.8%	8.7%	9.7%	8.8%
scenery		14.2%	14.3%	12.0%	10.2%
wildlife		5.4%	6.1%	7.3%	7.4%
Survation National					
access		5.3%	6.2%	5.0%	6.3%
adventure		5.5%	5.6%	4.1%	3.3%
nature		8.8%	7.6%	7.6%	7.3%
scenery		12.2%	13.5%	11.9%	11.0%
wildlife		3.8%	5.1%	6.2%	6.1%

Table 5: Data on the proportion of attributes chosen for both local and national favourite wild places for different age groups in the Survation and JMT cohort. Bold indicates trends discussed in the main text.

Settlement	City	Town	Village	Hamlet	Non-settlement
JMT (National)					
access	3.6%	4.2%	3.7%	3.5%	3.4%
light	4.4%	4.4%	4.7%	4.9%	5.3%
nature	5.9%	6.1%	6.2%	5.9%	6.4%
paths	2.6%	2.9%	2.6%	2.5%	2.2%
quiet	8.0%	7.9%	7.8%	7.9%	7.7%
remoteness	6.8%	6.6%	6.7%	6.9%	6.8%
JMT (Local)					
<i>access</i>	8.4%	7.4%	6.0%	5.2%	4.7%
light	1.9%	2.4%	3.5%	4.6%	4.8%
nature	7.6%	7.5%	7.0%	6.8%	6.8%
paths	5.4%	4.9%	3.9%	3.0%	2.9%
quiet	9.5%	9.3%	9.3%	9.2%	8.9%
remoteness	2.4%	3.2%	4.0%	4.8%	4.7%
Survation (National)					
access	5.4%	6.0%	5.8%	5.4%	3.7%
light	3.1%	2.9%	3.2%	3.9%	4.2%
nature	7.7%	7.6%	7.6%	6.7%	5.3%
paths	4.2%	4.6%	4.4%	3.2%	2.6%
quiet	8.8%	9.3%	8.4%	7.6%	10.6%
remoteness	6.4%	6.2%	6.7%	6.9%	8.5%
Survation (Local)					
access	10.2%	9.6%	8.0%	7.1%	6.1%
light	1.6%	1.6%	2.5%	4.2%	5.1%
nature	9.1%	9.4%	9.1%	6.6%	7.1%
paths	8.0%	7.2%	5.9%	5.1%	4.1%
quiet	10.9%	11.4%	11.5%	8.2%	11.7%
remoteness	2.2%	2.9%	3.7%	4.9%	5.1%

Table 6: Data on the proportion of attributes chosen for both local and national favourite wild places for different settlement types in the Survation and JMT cohort, where settlements have been grouped based on their urban category. Bold indicates trends discussed in the main text.

3.4 Semantic Analysis using Natural Language Processing

To better understand the type of free text responses shared and identify new reasons for choosing a wild place as a favourite location, we used semantic analysis with natural language processing (NLP) to cluster different responses together. The majority of NLP models in recent times have built upon the transformer architecture [6], which autoregressively tokenises and embeds words in a sentence. In order to produce a holistic representation of a sentence, these tokens need to be pooled into a single embedding. In this work, we used the `distil-roberta-v1` model ¹. This model is trained on a number of question answering and summarisation datasets, and is commonly used to produce sentence-level embeddings.

Once embeddings are generated for each sentence, the UMAP dimensionality techniques were used to reduce the dimension of the data to allow for clustering. Cluster quality metrics were not used to assess the goodness-of-fit of the clusters as there was no ground truth. The granularity of the clustering is best determined by the desired level of semantic description (i.e., the number of different responses that are expected to be well described by a single semantic label), and this did not lend itself easily to a metric.

After these clusters have been generated, the semantic nature of each cluster needed to be then ascertained. While this can be done manually, cluster allocations could change significantly according to the granularity of the clustering of the dimensionality reduction, and automated process is much preferred. Three methods for automated cluster analysis were implemented:

Summarisation Language models pretrained to provide summaries of a text extract were employed to summarise the responses belonging to a given cluster. Here the `long-t5-tglobal-base-16384-book-summary` model ² were used. This did not produce useful results: the summaries strongly reflect the corpus used to to training the language model. For example, one cluster was labelled as: ‘The narrator recounts his

¹<https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-distilroberta-v1>

²<https://huggingface.co/pszemraj/long-t5-tglobal-base-16384-book-summary>

childhood memories and the places that have made him who he is today. He tells of his love for whiskey and how he came to be so close to his family when he was young. He also recounts some of the happy times he has had with his friends and family.’.

Question Answering Instruction-based language models, such as Instruct-GPT, have generated a significant amount of attention recently. Here a fine-tuned bert model ³ was used. The language model is given the member sentences of a cluster as context, and prompted with the question “Summarize the context phrases”. In contrast to the previous method, the generated labels tend to replicate a phrase present in the sentences.

Word Count Aggregator The simplest way to produce an interpretable label is to use the four most common words present in the cluster.

Clusters and labels using question answering and word count are shown in Fig. 3 for UK favourite wild places, and Fig. 4 for local wild places. The summarisation labels are omitted.

As there is not a clear metric for comparing automatically generated cluster labels, it is difficult to say definitively which labels are better or worse. By inspection we can see that arguably the labels generated by word count aggregation are more specific and informative than those generated by the question answering network. For example, the label “fond memories” appears to be a potentially fair synopsis, but when looking at the word count aggregator label of “got, married, wife, proposed”, it clear that there is a more specific reason for this clustering that can be obtained from the response data.

There are not obvious discernible differences or trends when comparing the cluster labels of the clusters through inspection. Statistics comparing the clusters between local and UK-wide wild places have not been computed, and indeed it would be difficult to infer any semantic significance from these statistics.

A general trend that can be seen in these data is the representation of sentimentality in the responses of participants. This would suggest that

³https://huggingface.co/krinal214/zero_shot

Figure 3: 2D projections of semantic embeddings of the free text responses for additional reasons for choosing favourite UK-wide wild places. **Legend top** Cluster labels using question answering **Legend bottom** Cluster labels using word count aggregation

Figure 4: 2D projections of semantic embeddings of the free text responses for additional reasons for choosing favourite local wild places. **Legend top** Cluster labels using question answering **Legend bottom** Cluster labels using word count aggregation

the survey prompts did not allow for a significant number of participants to highlight the importance of sentimental features such as familial connections to the land. An area being selected for sentimental reasons is likely not a good heuristic for determining a participant's perceived notion of "wildness", as these reasons are not intrinsic to the land itself. However, this does highlight a potential confound in the survey methodology, namely the use of the word "favourite" in the prompts.

4 Clustering points to define distinct wild places

The above analysis highlighted that wild places are multi-faceted, often being chosen by survey respondents due to multiple factors both measurable, such as accessibility or remoteness, as well as subjective, such as memories of the place. We note that wild places, as with any place, cannot realistically be represented by single points on a map. A place could be a single point location (e.g. "top of Ben Nevis"), linear feature (e.g. "the River Wye") or area (e.g. "the Lake District National Park").

These three types of features map to the three types of vector data used in most GIS systems: points, lines and polygons. Even the suitability of these three feature types in mapping places is a much debated topic, as place boundaries are usually fuzzy and based on the perception of place [7]. Therefore, to better understand how the chosen wild places are distributed across the UK, we carried out clustering analysis on the map point locations chosen by participants to identify groups of points representing approximately the same wild place. The aim of this analysis was to allow us to identify the most popular wild places (the largest clusters), label these places by relating them to existing landscape designations, and assess their physical attributes over an area rather than at single points.

Key Findings

1. We used a K nearest neighbour networks to group points and Leiden community detection to identify clusters, using using different values of the resolution parameter. We found that the resolution parameter allowed us to identify clusters with different geographic scales such as National Parks (low resolution), and Nature Reserves or National Trust sites (high resolutions).
2. We constructed a cluster naming approach using hierarchical clustering which allowed for unsupervised assignment of geographical names to the majority of the top 100 clusters.
3. We were able to relate all cluster sets to different land designation datasets.
4. We identified the top 20 regions containing wild places in the UK.

4.1 K nearest neighbour network construction and clustering

This approach uses the distances between points to construct a network where each point is linked to its k nearest neighbours. As the distances are thereafter no longer considered, this approach is suitable for cases where points are very unevenly distributed within and between clusters - for example, when some points are spread across a large national park, while others are tightly clustered around a specific scenic spot.

For this specific analysis, we focused on the UK wild places from the JMT survey, and clustered points based on their Euclidean distances in British National Grid coordinates.

We constructed K-nearest neighbour networks using different values of k (the number of nearest neighbours). There were up to 28 points at the exact same coordinates, likely due to participants using search function in the survey map to find the location of their favourite wild place. This guided our choice to start with a minimum k of 30. We then used Leiden community detection to identify clusters, using different values of the resolution parameter. Varying this allowed us to identify clusters with different geographic scales. For example, low resolution clusters might

Figure 5: The effect of varying k and resolution on number of identified clusters in Leiden clustering of KNN networks

correspond to large areas such as National Parks, while high resolution clusters might correspond to smaller areas of interest such as Nature Reserves or National Trust sites.

The number of clusters was strongly affected by the resolution parameter, with less than 50 clusters at resolution 0.5 or 1, and 100-150 clusters at resolution 20 (Figure 5). The value of k also affected the number of clusters, with fewer clusters found when considering higher numbers of nearest neighbours. The average cluster size was also affected by both parameters, with larger numbers of clusters leading to a smaller average cluster size (Figure 6), as expected.

We assessed the quality of these clusters using two approaches. Firstly, cluster-intrinsic metrics were used to measure cluster compactness and the separation between clusters. We calculated multiple cluster-intrinsic metrics including the average silhouette width, Davies-Bouldin Index, and Calinski-Harabasz pseudo F-statistic. However, these did not reveal a clear set of clustering parameters that optimised multiple metrics.

Therefore, we also incorporated additional data to measure cluster quality

Figure 6: The effect of varying k and resolution on cluster size in Leiden clustering of KNN networks

using an extrinsic metric. Analysis of the points collected from the Wild Places Survey found that the majority of provided place names refer to areas and, therefore, we attempted to relate each record to a pre-existing polygon feature in one of the landscape designation datasets (representing different land designations, such as AONB, National Parks, and Special Conservation Areas) listed in Table 9. Place names were extracted using spatial joins of the data so that each wild place point was assigned a list of possible names based on polygons that they intersected with. Where there were separate land designation datasets for same type of land designation in England, Wales, and Scotland, we combined these into one set of point assignments.

We then took these point assignments as hypothetical true cluster labels to calculate the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI). The ARI measures the agreement between two sets of cluster labels, adjusted for the frequency of overlaps expected by chance. An ARI of 1 represents perfect agreement, while a value of zero indicates that the agreement is no higher than expected at random. Across all values of k and the resolution parameter, the ARI was generally below 0.75, indicating poor agreement.

Number of clusters	Mean cluster size	Number of singletons
500	19.4	229
1000	9.7	508
2000	4.9	1192
3000	3.2	1993

Table 7: Using different numbers of hierarchical clusters leads to different distributions of cluster size.

However, some clear patterns were apparent, including that the “Parks and Gardens” dataset was poorly captured by any set of clustering parameters, and that the National Parks (NP) and AONB datasets were among the best captured datasets, specifically at high values of k and the lowest resolution value.

One limitation of using the point assignment to land designation datasets is that each dataset only covers a small proportion of the UK. For any given dataset, many points will not be classified into any cluster as they fall outside the boundaries of the areas included. Therefore, for each dataset we removed unclassified points from the calculation. The impact of this is unclear, as we did not have time to investigate alternative approaches such as labelling all unclassified points as “other”.

4.2 Hierarchical clustering

An alternative approach is hierarchical clustering. We constructed a dendrogram based on the Euclidean distances between points in the John Muir Trust (JMT) UK datasets, using a single-linkage approach for merging clusters. Single-linkage allows for highly non-spherical cluster shapes, which we expect to see in our data, for example along coastlines or valleys. However, other linkage measures may also be appropriate for this data. We cut the dendrogram at different levels to obtain different cluster numbers, as shown in Table 7.

At each level, a high proportion of clusters contain only a single point. This makes sense for this dataset, as it’s likely that many favourite wild places will be unique to an individual respondent, especially given the relatively

Number of clusters	Mean	90th percentile	99th percentile
500	8.8	22.2	90.1
1000	4.3	10.8	55.7
2000	1.4	1.2	14.4
3000	0.61	1.9	6.8

Table 8: Geographical size of clusters, measured by the maximum distance between points in the same cluster, in km.

small sample size compared to the many possible wild places in the UK. However, this could also be due to the dendrogram construction approach chosen.

The geographical size of clusters also varies depending on the number of clusters obtained. We measured geographical size by taking the maximum distance between two points within the same cluster. At any number of clusters, there is a skewed distribution of this cluster span value, with a high proportion of small clusters and a small number of much larger clusters (Table 8). In order to better visualise the clusters, and for downstream analysis, we used the QGIS software to calculate the concave hull around all points in a cluster with a minimum of at least 3 points (Figure 7). Minimum bounding geometries calculated using the convex hull geometry type were also calculated, but found to over-estimate the area clusters by incorporating the areas between outlying points.

Due to time limitations, we focused on assessing cluster quality using the Adjusted Rand Index of each cluster set compared to external datasets as described for KNN network clustering above (Section 4.1). All the land designation datasets that we considered, except one (INSPIRE Conservation Areas), could be well classified by one or more of the cluster sets considered. The best number of clusters depended on the feature set, with, for example, “Parks & Gardens” being better represented by more smaller clusters and National Parks by fewer larger clusters.

Figure 7: Cluster areas of hierarchical clusters

Figure 8: Adjusted Rand Index measuring the agreement between hierarchical clustering and hypothetical true cluster labels derived from land designation datasets. An Adjusted Rand Index of 1 represents perfect agreement between the two sets of cluster labels, while a value of zero indicates that the agreement is no higher than expected at random.

Figure 9: The number of possible names assigned to each cluster by taking the most commonly occurring names assigned to individual points.

4.3 Cluster name assignment

In order to relate the most popular wild places with existing land designations and facilitate data interpretation, we attempted to annotate clusters with names based on the most common word, or set of words input to the survey question “What is this wild place called?”. However, this approach was disregarded due to difficulties in reconciling place names with different spellings, languages (Gaelic/Welsh/English), colloquialisms or informal names, and multipart names such as “Scarfell Pike, the Lake District”. Therefore, we attempted to label clusters in an unsupervised way. For this proof of principle we used clusters derived from the hierarchical clustering approach described above. However, the same approach could be used with an arbitrary set of input clusters.

A list of possible place names for each point was derived using a spatial join so that points falling within a land designation polygon had the name of that polygon appended. Data used to identify area names is given in table Table 9. The list of most commonly occurring place names within

Dataset	Coverage	Provider
OpenStreetMap	UK	OpenStreetMap
AONB	England, Wales	Natural England, LLE
Battlefields	England, Scotland, Wales	Natural England, Scottish Government, Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales
Conservation Areas	England, Wales	Historic England, Welsh Government
Gardens and Designated Landscapes	Scotland	Historic Environment Scotland
Historic Parks & Gardens	Wales	Welsh Government
Local Nature Reserves	England, Scotland, Wales	Natural England, Nature.Scot, Welsh Government
National Nature Reserves	England, Scotland, Wales	Natural England, Nature.Scot, Welsh Government
National Parks	UK	Ordnance Survey
National Scenic Areas	Scotland	Nature.Scot
National Trust Properties	England, Wales	The National Trust
Ordnance Survey Open Greenspace	GB	Ordnance Survey
Parks and Gardens	England	Historic England
RAMSAR Sites	UK	Joint Nature Conservation Committee
RSPB Reserves	UK	RSPB
Scheduled Monuments	England, Scotland, Wales	Historic England, Historic Environment Scotland, Welsh Government
Special Areas of Conservation	GB	Joint Nature Conservation Committee
Special Protection Areas	GB	Joint Nature Conservation Committee
World Heritage Sites	England, Scotland, Wales	Historic England, Historic Environment Scotland, Welsh Government

Table 9: External datasets used in this study.

Figure 10: Cluster name status. Unambiguously named clusters have a single most commonly occurring name assigned to their constituent points. Ambiguous clusters have multiple equally common names. Unnamed clusters have no name which occurs more than 50% of the time.

each cluster were then assigned to that cluster, so that the cluster size determined the cluster name in some locations. For example, where a small cluster of points is located within “Loch Lomond” polygon, but also within larger clusters such as “Loch Lomond and the Trossachs National Park” and “The Scottish Highlands”.

We found that in many cases, multiple names were equally common within a cluster (Figure 9). This can occur when two polygons largely overlap, such as the World Heritage Site “the English Lake District” and the “Lake District National Park” from the OS Greenspaces dataset. It can also occur by chance when the cluster is very small, or few points within the cluster are assigned a name. Therefore, in order to have higher confidence cluster name assignments, we removed names that were only assigned to a single point within a cluster or that occurred in less than 50% of the points in a cluster. These clusters were classified as having no assigned name.

For clusters that still had multiple possible names with equal frequency, we considered their naming status to be ambiguous. Clusters with a single most common name were considered to be unambiguously named. Of the top 100 largest clusters at all total cluster numbers, the majority could be assigned an unambiguous name without manual curation (Figure 10). As an example, we show here the top 20 largest clusters from 1000 hierarchical clusters (Figure 11). All of these clusters could be assigned an unambiguous name without manual curation, except for the largest cluster, for which the labels “Lake District National Park” and “The English Lake District” were equally common.

These were

- | | |
|--|---|
| 1. Lake District National Park | 11. Yorkshire Dales National Park |
| 2. Snowdonia National Park | 12. Wester Ross |
| 3. Cairngorms National Park | 13. Morar, Moidart and Ardhamurchan |
| 4. Ben Nevis & Glen Coe | 14. Brecon Beacons National Park |
| 5. The Cuillin Hills | 15. Cornwall |
| 6. Peak District National Park | 16. Northumberland Coast |
| 7. Dartmoor National Park | 17. Oldshoremore and Sandwood |
| 8. Assynt Coigach | 18. Dorset |
| 9. Loch Lomond & The Trossachs National Park | 19. New Forest National Park |
| 10. Knoydart | 20. Joint: North Arran/Exmoor National Park |

The cluster naming approach described above serves as a proof of principle for unsupervised assignment of names to the majority of the top 100 clusters. However, many clusters have no assigned name or have multiple possible names assigned to them. Some ambiguous names could be filtered out by manual curation of the land designation polygons used for name assignment, or the construction of a hierarchy of land designations based on their size and overlap. It may also be possible to

Top 20 favourite UK wild places (1000 clusters)

Figure 11: The top 20 largest clusters from 1000 hierarchical clusters, labelled with names assigned by considering the most common name assigned to their constituent points. Due to a tie for 20th place, 21 clusters are included.

collapse multiple possible names based on their textual similarity. Future work should investigate these extensions.

5 Difference between Local & National Wild Places

One objective of this study is to identify the selection criteria and main features that people consider when choosing their favourite wild places in the UK and near to their home. All the survey information was repeated for a participants favourite local wild place as well as their favourite national wild place. Given this additional detail, we were interested to see how the local and national wild places varied. To do so, we first looked at clustering the local and national points and considered how the distribution of chosen locations differed over the UK. We then used the features from the survey to classify whether a location was local or national and investigated which features contributed most to successful classification.

Key Findings

1. We used a clustering algorithm (DBSCAN) on local and national favourite wild places and saw a difference in spatial distribution where local places were far more dispersed across the UK compared to those chosen as national favourite.
2. We created a binary classification model that distinguishes between local and national favourite wild places and that had an accuracy of over 70% for the JMT survey when all survey data was used (both ordinal and multi-selection).
3. We performed feature importance analysis to identify the most important features in the dataset, based on how much each feature contributes to the accuracy of the classifier. We found that remoteness was the most important feature but activities, adventure, accessibility, culture and community involvement all scored high.
4. We created visualisations to understand how features varied across

the UK which highlighted, for example, regions of low importance for *activity* in Scotland.

5.1 Clustering applied to local and national wild places

To carry out the analysis, we constructed a Density-Based Spatial Clustering (DBSCAN) algorithm with `sk-learn` using optimised values for `epsilon` (the maximum distance between two samples for one to be considered as in the neighborhood of the other) and `min_samples` (the number of samples, or total weight, in a neighborhood for a point to be considered as a core point). [8] Compared to hierarchical clustering and K-means clustering, DBSCAN is more resistant to outliers and can handle clusters of different sizes and shapes, which works well with our dataset given that there were some wild places selected by only a small number of respondents (less than 20) and there are wild places along the coastline, which would appear differently from those in the center of the land.

We performed DBSCAN clustering on the local and UK data from the JMT and Survation surveys and plotted an interactive map using `folium`. Screenshots of the interactive map were taken for demonstration in this report. Figure 12 shows a comparison of local and UK wild places determined from the Survation dataset using DBSCAN with $\epsilon = 0.1$ and `min_samples = 20`. The green spots represent popular wild places with more than 20 people choosing this place as their favourite wild place, while the red spots are sparse points (fewer than 20 people selected this place). A difference in the distribution of wild places can be observed. As highlighted in Figure 12(a), the Lake District is classified as a popular wild place in the nationwide wild place survey but not as a local wild place.

5.2 Classifying local & national wild places

Given the clear differences in the spatial distribution of local and national wild places, along with the differences in attributes, as described in Section 3, we next consider which of these features are most significant in determining whether a local wild place is local or national. As described

(a) UK wild places

(b) Local wild places

Figure 12: Comparison of local and UK wild places defined from the survey by Survation.

in 3, remoteness is a clear determining factor due to the difference in travel ease. However, we are interested in which of the attributes hold additional predictive power. In order to determine this, we created a binary classification model that distinguishes between local and UK wild places. We chose a “random forest” classifier, an ensemble learning method that combines the predictions of multiple decision trees. Random forest has been shown to have high accuracy in classification tasks, it can handle sparse datasets, is resistant to over-fitting and can provide a feature importance measurement. We use the feature importance analysis to identify the most important features in the dataset, based on how much each feature contributes to the accuracy of the classifier.

5.3 Classification results

A random forest classifier was trained on three different settings: one using only ordinal variables, another using only multiple selection variables, and the third using both types of variables merged together. Table 10 shows

Figure 13: Confusion matrix for the UK/Local Random Forest Classification trained with the ordinal and multi-selection variables from the JMT Survey.

the accuracy obtained for each setting. For the JMT Survey, the highest accuracy was achieved when using both types of variables. However, for the Survation Survey, the best accuracy was achieved when using only the multiple selection data.

Despite the limitations of the random forest analysis, the feature importance results in Fig. 14 provide valuable insight into which features are most influential in differentiating between Local and UK wild places. We found that, along with *Remoteness*, *Activities*, *Adventure*,

Data Configurations	RF Accuracy	
	Survation Survey	JMT Survey
Ordinal	0.51	0.56
Multi-selection	0.64	0.68
Ordinal & Multi-selection	0.61	0.71

Table 10: Random Forest accuracy for Survation Survey and JMT Survey data configurations.

Figure 14: Random Forest feature importance for the JMT Survey dataset, using ordinal and multi-selection variables. Selection of 10 features with the highest importance.

Accessibility, *Culture* and *Community involvement* all contributed a significant amount to distinguishing between whether a wild place is locally or nationally favoured.

To understand how the features contributed to the classification results, we visualised the distribution for each variable, as weighted by its importance. This can be done by creating a two-dimensional histogram for the multi-selection variables like *Remoteness*, *Accessibility*, and *Scenery*, as shown in Figure 15. These figures highlight not only the position of a chosen wild place but also their importance in that specific attribute.

This work highlighted the difference between local and national wild places. We found that there were some differences, but these may be partly driven by the survey methodology, as local wild places were requested to be within 30 minutes from the respondents home. This meant that local places were more broadly dispersed across the UK, with fewer clusters and more singletons. Additionally, when identifying features that distinguished between local and national favourite places, we saw some features that maybe an artefact of the survey design such

(a) Remoteness (Local)

(b) Remoteness (UK)

(c) Accessibility (Local)

(d) Accessibility (UK)

(e) Scenery (Local)

(f) Scenery (UK)

Figure 15: Two-dimensional histograms for feature in the multi-selection section of the JMT Survey.

as *Remoteness* having high importance, as well as features like *Accessibility* and *Community involvement*. This shouldn't be considered a negative and highlights that, when travel is restricted, participants rely on different concepts to find a wild place and may be more creative in where they choose.

6 Constructing a Wild Place Index

We have discussed both the distribution of subjective attributes reported by survey respondents as well as the physical distribution of wild places across the UK. In order to better understand how these wild places compare to other metrics for wildness as well as how respondent impressions relate to objective measures of similar attributes, we used a number of physical and spatial open-source datasets.

In order to best relate subjective descriptions to objective and quantified metrics within the time period, we focused only on the subset of characteristics of wild places that we know as being important for both the Suration and the John Muir Trust (JMT) cohort. These characteristics were *scenery, sights and sounds of nature, activities to do, ability to access, community involvement, presence or absence of people, sense of peace and quiet, cultural importance*. We did not, for example, consider *water* as this was not typically referred to by survey respondents though would likely have been easy to quantify using external physical datasets.

Key Findings

1. We were able to relate the most important features identified in the social dataset to external datasets on physical and geo-spatial metrics.
2. We constructed a linear regression model to identify weights for a wild place score. The regressor was able to predict the wild place score with over 85% accuracy for both local, national, and the combination of both. Feature importance for this regressor gave insight into possible weighting mechanisms for the scoring function.

3. We found that our models evaluated the features '*activity*' and '*culture*' as the two most important, and '*quiet*' as the least important. These differed from earlier calculations of feature importance due to the role of external datasets. This highlights these should be weighted higher to reflect social datasets.
4. We investigated how the role of different features vary within age groups and found that *activity* was a significant feature in distinguishing wild places for different ages.
5. We built a preliminary "Wild Place Index (WPI)", where each grid square has a wildness score that is based on a combination of physical and social datasets. We explored different resolutions for this WPI and used the WPI to calculate a wildness score where no data was available and build a classification model to infer what the most important 'wildness attribute' for a place might be. We were able to predict wildness scores with 70% accuracy and the most important attribute with 90 % importance.

6.1 Preparing external datasets for use as a wildness index

The datasets used for our wilderness index analysis included the same open source datasets used in the wild place name assignment (Figure Figure 11) and additional datasets outlined in Appendix C, with further details provided in Appendix C. These were all open-source and offered detailed information about specific aspects of the UK. Having chosen the datasets, we next relate these data to characteristics related to wild places. This is achieved as follows:

Activities The dataset provides the outdoor recreation potential maps according to the preferences of each of the five tourist groups, including convenience recreationists, day trippers, education recreationists, nature trekker, and spiritual re-creationist. As the map is for Europe, we extracted each map according to the administrative boundary of the UK.

Scenery Initial experiments used terrain data (OS Terrain50) combined with land cover (UKCEH Landcover) data to create histograms of land

cover classes that can theoretically be seen from each labelled wild place point. To define the scenery index as the product of visibility index and the land use diversity index, which conveys the degree of land use variety that can be viewed in each pixel. Specifically, the outgoing visibility index is calculated using the OS Terrains 50, which reflects the visual exposition and size of the observed surface from each pixel [9]. The Land Cover Gridded maps are employed to calculate the Land Use Diversity Index, which captures the variety of land use types in the surrounding area of each pixel. To compute a statistic of the values within a specified neighbourhood around each pixel location, focal statistics were applied with a chosen cell size of 3. Subsequently, the index was normalised to obtain the final output feature of scenery.

Sights and sounds of nature We assumed that the level of sights and sounds of nature can be correlated with the local biodiversity level. An area with higher biodiversity levels is likely to exhibit more pleasant sounds and a diverse range of sights. To determine this level, we used the Globio4 (2015) dataset. The administrative boundaries of the United Kingdom are used as a mask to extract the biodiversity values within the region.

Peace and Quiet, or Sense of Solitude It was assumed that the level of peace and quiet and sense of solitude experienced by individuals is closely associated with a location's distance from urban built-up areas. Therefore, the Euclidean Distances to urban built up areas were calculated based on the OS Built Up Area dataset. The distance raster layer was then normalised to create the index of this feature.

Presence or Absence of People To measure the degree of presence or absence of people in a given area, we used the LandScan Glob dataset, which describes the amount of population in each pixel. The administrative boundaries of the UK were used to extract the population values within the region. The population values were then normalised to create the final index of this feature

Community Involvement It was hypothesised that community involvement is positively associated to the presence of local charities, which can contribute to the improvement and development of community engagement. We collected registered charity numbers for each county in the four countries in the UK. These numbers were then appended to the county administrative boundary layers and normalised to create the final

index of community involvement.

Cultural Importance The level of culture importance in each county is quantified through the examination of natural and cultural heritage sites. we integrated 21 heritage lists in total. Polygon features were transferred to points using the centroids of the polygons, while point features were retained. The number of heritage sites within each county was then calculated, and the resulting values were normalised to obtain a cultural importance index for each county across the United Kingdom.

Accessibility Two methods were used to evaluate accessibility. First, Euclidean distances from each pixel to the OS Road Networks were calculated. Second, accessibility to the location points was determined by generating the shortest distances from each point to its nearest road. We then perform min-max normalisation on the points and the accessibility index was defined as $1 - \text{the normalised distance}$. The reason behind this is that if a location is close to a road, the normalised distance will be close to 0, so the accessibility index should be close to 1.

The GIS layers for the above datasets are shown in shown in Figure 16. This highlights that we were able to relate the given features within the social data to external features in a robust way and which provides a new means to interpret how the concept of 'wildness' intersects with quantifiable metrics such as population density, distribution of heritage sites and the distribution of built up areas. In particular, we find that some of these maps show striking resemblance to the clustering of national wild places in the JMT survey, described in Section 4. These include activities and sights and sounds of nature. Other features seem to not necessarily relate to the social datasets, such as scenery and the presence (or absence) of people. The former appears to have higher ranking towards the north-west of England whereas the latter is highly skewed by the high population density of England. Additionally, certain regions have been affected by artefacts from lack of available data, as in Accessibility and Peace & Quiet which has an overly skewed value towards the Northern Ireland.

(a) Activities

(b) Scenery

(c) Sights and sounds of nature

(d) Presence of People

(e) Community Involvement

(f) Cultural Importance

Figure 16: Feature indexes from external datasets.

6.2 Defining a Wild Place Score

While the definition of wildness remains ambiguous, one can still come up with a way of scoring a wild place given features that are important to a place being wild. The features were extracted from the survey questions decided by the JMT, described in Section 2. We took the approach of Carver et al. 2012 and created a linear scoring function that combines the 8 attributes weighted by their relative importance. That is, the wildness score S_i of location i is defined as

$$S_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^n W_j X_{ij}(\mathbf{x})$$

where n is the number of features, W is the weighted importance of the feature, X is the normalised feature score, and \mathbf{x} is the location of interest. The values of the weights W_j are discussed below. We normalised the wildness score index to be in the range $[0, 1]$ where 1 indicates a perfect score on each of the eight features described in Section 6.

To assess how well the wild score index does, we show in Figure 17 the distribution of the scores from the places chosen by respondents in the survey. As these are all chosen as a ‘favourite’ wild place, we observed that for both the UK and local wild places, most of the locations score somewhere between 0.4 to 0.7 with the majority of points greater than 0.5. Interestingly, we observed that a large proportion of wild places chosen as a favourite local place are less than 0.5, indicating that participants value those locations for more than what is supported by external datasets, such as past experiences and sentiment.

6.3 Feature analysis to determine scoring weights

We used the external dataset measures to develop a score for each wild place provided by survey respondents. However, we assumed that all features should be given equal weight. In Section 3, we observed a distinction between local and national wild places and, in Section 5, we quantified this difference in attributes using a random forest classifier. Here, we consider another method for determining feature importance for a wild place and define the weights using a linear regressor. The feature

Figure 17: Distribution of wildness score from the JMT and Survation wild locations, based on external datasets

weights were compared between local, UK and a combination of local and UK.

We first summarised all 8 features with the same weights, and generated a score, then normalised this to be in between 0 and 1. For the normalisation, the minimum was set as 0 and the maximum was set as 8 (as the maximum possible summation of all features is 8). Each dataset was randomly split into training and testing sets with 30% of data for testing and we predicted the subjective score (the equivalent survey score for these attributes) based on the external datasets. We then calculated the feature weights which are the normalised coefficients generated from the linear regression model. The regressor for the local dataset achieved an R^2 score of 87.6% for training and 88.1% for testing. For the national dataset, it achieved a score 92.8% and 93.1% and 90.5% and 90.3% for the combination of both local and national datasets. These indicate that none of the models were over-fitting or had insufficient performance. The final feature weights are shown in Table 11. In particular, the weights for local and local & UK are similar, and the ranking of features was the same. The features *'people'* and *'accessibility'* in the UK model were found to have more weight than in the other two models.

All three models evaluated the features ‘*activity*’ and ‘*culture*’ as the two most important, while ‘*quiet*’ was the least important.

Feature		activity	people	community	culture	scenery	sights	quiet	access
Weight	Local	.25	.07	.19	.30	.08	.13	-.01	.01
	UK	.21	.11	.18	.26	.06	.12	.00	.06
	Local+UK	.23	.09	.18	.29	.07	.12	-.01	.03

Table 11: Feature Weights.

Interestingly, we find that the feature weights were different from the findings in other analyses, such as in Section 3 and Section 5. This difference can be understood as relating to the introduction of external datasets, as the other analyses were based on subjective data (i.e. the people’s perceptive responses).

To further explore this, we conducted statistical tests for each feature between different age groups. Statistic testing was conducted, as in [11], to identify the difference in nature-based activities between each tourist cluster. As shown in Table 12, all features, apart from *scenery*, had significant differences among the age groups with small effect sizes. The assumptions of normal distribution and equal variance were violated. Thus a non-parametric test, the Welch’s ANOVA test (F), was chosen to compute the statistical difference ($p < .05^*$) for each feature between each age group. We also performed a post-hoc test for the pairwise difference, as reported in Table 13. We found that no significantly different group pairs were observed in *culture*. For the other features, we see that the majority of the groups were different to each other. This can explain the high performance in our regressor models; specifically, there is more variances in the *activity* which the model is likely to have learnt. This is also the case of *community*, *sights* and *culture* which have relatively higher F-statistic than the other features.

6.4 Relating Wildness Score to physical locations

Having constructed a wild scoring function and investigated different methods for weighting features in this function, we next turn to how this scoring function performs on aggregated spatial data. Specifically, we discretise the UK into square sub-regions and, motivated by the analysis

Feature		activity	people	community	culture	scenery	sights	quiet	access
Weight	Local	.25	.07	.19	.30	.08	.13	-.01	.01
	UK	.21	.11	.18	.26	.06	.12	.00	.06
	Local+UK	.23	.09	.18	.29	.07	.12	-.01	.03
Regression Features									
<i>F</i>		6.192	3.061	5.153	2.457	1.464	5.303	4.031	1.534
<i>p</i>		.000*	.001*	.000*	.033*	.202	.000*	.001*	.000*
Effect Size		.003	.001	.001	.001	.000	.000	.000	.001

Table 12: Feature weights based on survey data (top) and using linear regression (bottom). The statistical power is .827. The effect size is Partial Eta-Squared, $\eta p^2 < .01$ indicates a small effect, based on Welch’s ANOVA test (bottom).

Feature	Group A	Group B	<i>T</i>	<i>p</i>	Effect Size
quiet	41 - 60	under 18	3.834	.003	.102
	over 60	under 18	3.329	.013	.109
community	18 - 25	41 - 60	3.688	.003	.085
		over 60	3.758	.002	.113
	26 - 40	41 - 60	3.023	.030	.050
		over 60	3.053	.028	.077
sight	18 - 25	41 - 60	3.943	.001	.090
	41 - 60	over 60	-3.628	.004	-.088
activity	18 - 25	41 - 60	3.088	.025	.062
		under 18	-4.544	.000	.128
	26 - 40	no answer	-2.994	.046	-.119
		under 18	-6.844	.000	-.142
	41 - 60	no answer	-3.793	.005	-.135
		under 18	-8.109	.000	-.155
over 60	under 18	-4.995	.000	-.145	
people	26 - 40	41 - 60	3.124	.022	.051

Table 13: The post-hoc Games-Howell test, *T* (only the group pairs that show significant difference $p < .05$ are reported). The effect size is Cohen’s *d*, $d \leq .2$ indicates a small effect size.

from Section 4, explore different resolutions for how coarse-grain to make these grids. We then aggregate both survey and geospatial data within each grid square to get an overall wildness score using Equation 6.2. This provides us with a Wild Place Index (WPI), where each grid square has a wildness score that is based on a combination of physical and social datasets. We describe the steps taken in more detail below.

We first construct the grid that is used to aggregate survey data on favourite wild places and the corresponding wildness score for each place. In Figure 18, we show both grid resolutions . These were chosen to approximately match the upper and lower resolutions of hierarchical clusters used in Section 4, which was 22km and 7km.

(a) Low resolution

(b) High resolution

Figure 18: Comparison of different grid resolution where (a) shows low resolution with grid length of 22km and (b) low resolution with grid length of 7km

We then aggregate all points that are contained within a single sub-region. In Figure 19, we show figures for Survation (national and local), for low resolution grid size. Colours within each grid represents the overall number of points contained within a single grid cell. We note that we were able to broadly identify the same popular regions as those found from clustering analysis.

Whereas the distribution of points across the UK is high, it is clear that there are some sub-regions that were chosen by relatively few participants

(a) Survation - National

(b) Survation - Local

Figure 19: Comparison of different subregions with aggregated survey points for low resolution grid. Dense pockets are more clearly identified as with regions that are not particularly popular such as in (b) where Scotland has few wild places for the Survation cohort choosing favourite local wild place.

and a considerable number of sub-regions that were not chosen at all. This highlights that a significant proportion of the UK is not characterised in terms of the publics perceptions of its wildness.

In order to investigate this, we used the wildplace score (based on the external datasets), described above, and aggregated values for each point to create a wild place index. We show a comparison in Figure 20 for the favourite (nationwide) wild place of JMT, and the constructed WPI . We observe that Scotland and Yorkshire score high both in terms of the number of locations suggested by JMT participants as well as their respective scoring on the WPI. The Lake District scored lower than the popularity found from the survey. On the other hand, we find that

Cornwall and Devon are ranked much higher on the WPI than in JMT survey data. Further analysis is required to perform a more thorough comparison between the WPI and social datasets.

(a) JMT - National (b) Wild Place Index

Figure 20: Comparison of (a) the aggregated favourite national wild place for the JMT cohort against (b) the Wild Place Index (WPI).

Finally, we consider whether we can use the external datasets, along with the social datasets, to infer wildness scores for regions where there is no data (empty cells). To do so, we convert the grid into a regression problem in which we seek to infer the social score, which is the aggregated score across ordinal values, for regions without data using the WPI data. We were able to predict regions with 70% accuracy using Random Forest and XGBoost regressors. for the JMT survey and based on small grid size (high resolution). This translates to a potential upper bound of 70% accuracy in predicting scores provided by JMT respondents at a resolution of 7km. We note however that our model will be highly biased to the training data which is for places that already have

a high wildness score.

7 Conclusions

The work conducted within this Data Study Group has highlighted that the reasons for choosing a favourite wild places in the UK are multi-faceted. By considering two distinct datasets, based on social survey data and physical geospatial data, we were able to investigate the different attributes and characteristics of how wild places are perceived in the UK. These two datasets reflect different aspects of a place's 'wildness'. The first overlaps both with personal perception but also, as we highlight in Section 3, an individuals memories and past experiences.

In Section 3, we observed that certain attributes of a wild place can rank highly across different demographics and surveyed cohorts of the population. For example, we observed that a *sense of adventure* is typically more important to younger groups and a *lack of light pollution* more important to those that live far from cities. Additionally, using natural language processing, we were able to extract sentimental reasons for choosing a wild place, such as *dog walking* or *location for an engagement*. This indicates that wild places are important to individuals, often for very personal reasons.

Despite the differences in reasons for choosing a wild place, we observed that the majority of wild places still clustered in nearby regions, especially where survey respondents were free to choose anywhere in the UK. In Section 4, we compared two clustering methods, K nearest neighbour and hierarchical, to identify bounding regions for these clusters. We found that hierarchical clustering was more successful in identifying clusters (as measured using the adjusted Rand index) and we developed a novel unsupervised naming procedure to relate these clusters to regions in the UK. This allowed us to state the top 20 regions that contained the UK public's favourite wild places.

When considering how the favourite wild places were distributed in the UK, we found that travel time was an important consideration. The favourite wild place for the UK public were typically more highly concentrated around specific regions than the chosen local wild places. Moreover, we observed

that reasons for choosing a wild place also changed based on whether it was 'local' or 'national', as we discussed in Section 5. Using a random forest classifier, we were able to identify that *remoteness* was the attribute most important in distinguishing whether something might be a national or local favourite to an individual.

While our work showed that the UK public's understanding of wild places is complex, we also found that their reasons for choosing a wild place can intersect with objective measures of physical places. For some of the most frequently chosen attributes in forming a decision about a wild place, such as *scenery, sights and sounds of nature, activities to do* and *ability to access*, we were able to relate these to quantitative measures using external datasets, as described in Section 6.

In order to relate these two datasets, both social and physical, we investigated building a Wild Place Index (WPI), which combines both survey locations as well as measures constructed using external datasets. The basis for the WPI depends on a wildness score, which is given in Eq. 6.2. We used external datasets to work as features in this score. Future work should investigate both the applicability of this for scoring wild places as well as potentially introducing the social dataset as additional features. However, in doing so, care needs to be taken such that the imbalance in demographics is not transferred from the dataset to the scoring function.

One important finding from constructing our WPI was that the most significant features, which were used to weight the scoring function, differed from those identified in Section 3 and Section 5. This was expected given that previous studies did not use external datasets. Broadly speaking, analysis using social data only can be interpreted as highlighting what were some of the most important attributes *to an individual*. When combining this with external datasets, we considered what the most important external measures were in determining whether an individual would consider this a preferably wild place. This work contributes to theory building on the understanding of the complex characteristics of wild places in general and also in human perceptions of wild places. Future work might further investigate this, comparing this to the methods used in Section 5.

We note that this work provides a framework for understanding whether a

place might be important to the public in terms of its wildness even where no social data is available. By using these external datasets, and others, we might be able to infer whether a region or park needs to be given greater conservation attention due to the wildness score. We were able to infer the wildness score for regions without data with an accuracy of 70% and attributes associated with these regions with an accuracy of 90%.

Finally, we note that whether a place is seen as being seen as a favourite wild place, either locally or nationally, results in the total set of wild places chosen by the public is a subset of the places that might be considered as wild more broadly. For instance, when asked to list all those places that might be seen as wild near to ones home or nationally could result in an exhaustive list that also contains undesirable wild places such as unused buildings, fly-tipping spots or neglected parks. These are vital for biodiversity but are unlikely to feature as a favourite wild place to an individual. Hence, there are intrinsic limitations with the analysis that can be performed on the social dataset and further work might be needed to better understand how to interpret a wild place from both a social and conservation perspective.

8 Team members

Rashid Barket is a PhD candidate at Coventry University. He contributed to this project by analysing the survey responses, specifically the multiple option select and free text columns as well as creation of the wild place index.

Mauricio A. Diaz is a PhD candidate at the University of Southampton. He contributed to this project by identifying features that differentiate national and local wild places, through variable distribution analysis and classification methods.

Zixin Feng is a PhD candidate at University of Glasgow. She contributed to the project by analyzing external datasets and calculating feature indexes with GIS for wildness quantification.

Nick Homer is a PhD candidate at the University of Edinburgh and an intern at the John Muir Trust during this DSG. He contributed to this

project by carrying out and assisting with survey design and data collection, geospatial analysis, data preparation and cleaning, outlining the challenge and working with other participants of the DSG throughout.

Liz Ing-Simmons is a postdoctoral investigator Scientist at the MRC London Institute of Medical Sciences. She contributed to this project by carrying out KNN network and hierarchical clustering analyses .

Kaixin Ji is a PhD candidate at RMIT University. She contributed to this project by collaborating on the spatial external dataset analyses, and the wildness score index (weight analysis).

Cristín Lambert is one of the challenge organisers for this DSG. She contributed to this project by outlining the challenge objectives and scope, assisting with questions regarding the data, and in preparing the DSG for participants.

Matthew Sargent is a PhD candidate at University College London. He contributed to this project by conducting the free-text analysis using language models. He was also a group facilitator.

Namid Stillman is a researcher at Simudyne and was a postdoctoral researcher at UCL during part of this DSG. He was the Principal Investigator on this project. He contributed by coordinating between researchers and challenge organisers and was the lead author of this report. He additionally conducted the work on relating a Wild Place Index to sub-regions and using this to predict new wild places.

Fanzhi Su is a PhD candidate at University of Cambridge. He contributed to this project by carrying out DBSCAN clustering analysis to determine popular UK and local wild places and the combination of John Muir Trust and Survation dataset.

Alan Warr earned a management science PhD at the London Business School and is building a freelance career in London as a corporate data analyst and data scientist. He contributed to this project by performing data analyses and data visualisations that developed insights into how the perceptions of wild places vary across different types of respondents.

Note: All members of the team assisted with writing this report.

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A Appendix A

In Table 14, we show the full wording for the different survey options and the corresponding shorthand references used throughout this approach. We note that some of these are notably more descriptive than the shorthand used, such as “maintained paths” which denotes both good accessibility but also a level of maintenance. Similarly so, *Land Management* is specific to less intensively managed landscapes, denoting less urbanised or pastoral locations and intuitively a strong contributing factor to wild places. The additional information given here should be considered throughout the analysis presented in the report.

Survey Option Wording	Shorthand
Thriving nature and biodiversity	<i>Nature</i>
Scenery	<i>Scenery</i>
Lack of manmade structures	<i>Manmade Structures</i>
Remoteness	<i>Remoteness</i>
Peace, quiet and solitude	<i>Quiet</i>
Good accessibility	<i>Access</i>
Maintained paths	<i>Paths</i>
Activities and outdoor recreation	<i>Activities</i>
Lack of light pollution	<i>Light</i>
Clean air/water	<i>Air-Water</i>
No litter	<i>Litter</i>
Mental or physical health benefits of spending time there	<i>Health</i>
Being exposed to the weather/elements	<i>Weather</i>
Sense of adventure	<i>Adventure</i>
Wildlife spotting	<i>Wildlife</i>
Scientific interest (geology, biology etc.)	<i>Science</i>
Less intensively managed landscapes or land	<i>Land Management</i>
People and communities caring for the wild place	<i>Communities</i>
Historical significance	<i>History</i>
Other (please use text box below)	<i>Other</i>

Table 14: Survey option wordings and shorthand in response to the survey question: “What makes this wild place special? Select all that apply.”.

B Appendix B

Here we add additional data and graphs on the different data features observed in the survey data. In Figure 21, we show the variation in the number of categories chosen per cohort and in Figure 22, we show how the popularity of different characteristics vary between the two cohorts. We further break this down by local and national chosen wild place in Figure 23.

The proportion of respondents for each demographic category is provided in Figure 24, above. In general, we found that *Age*, *Health*, *Dwelling*, and *Ethnicities* all had pronounced differences in which characteristics were chosen. For example, Figure 25 presents the characteristics of favourite wild places for four broad age groups. It shows that there are small but significant differences between age groups. Generally, older age groups associate most characteristics more with their favourite wild places than younger age groups. *Access*, *Quiet* and *Scenery* are the three most pronounced differences across age groups. Though *Activities* and *Adventure* are observed as more popular for younger age groups.

Figure 26 presents the data by ethnicity and reveals a lot of differences. However, at the current level of analysis and visualisation the differences look quite random and difficult to interpret. The largest ethnic group in the UK is white, but we find evidence that non-white ethnicities may have different views and needs on what characterises favoured wild places based on the survey data. This warrants further attention.

When considering health status (which reflects both physical and mental), we found that *access*, *health benefits* and *quiet* were more pronounced for those with health conditions, but that other characteristics were broadly similar, as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 28 looks at settlement type from city and town dwellers through rural types. For the Survation survey, we observe marked differences with the more rural settlement types mentioning most characteristics more frequently. Intuitively this difference may be explained by rural dweller being more attuned to the characteristics of wild places from their “lived experience”, or more engaged to respond with surveys on outdoor places due to heightened concerns of conservation and ecological impact.

Interestingly, we find that the differences in gender on the characteristics of their favourite local and national wild places is small, as shown in Figure 29. There is good agreement across these two genders. A third gender of diverse was captured and that gender has some marked differences, such as increased number of respondents choosing *health* and *nature* are elevated. Overall, there were far fewer respondents in this type (less than 1% for both cohorts), so further investigation is required to understand the significance of this.

Figure 21: Number of categories chosen, broken up by cohort and whether discussing a local or national wild place

Figure 22: Differences in what characteristics led to a favourite wild places for the two survey cohorts

(a) National

(b) Local

Figure 24: Differences in the demographic data for the JMT and Suration cohorts

Figure 25: Characteristics Mentioned by Different Age Groups

Figure 26: Characteristics Mentioned by Different Ethnicities

Figure 27: Characteristics Mentioned by Health Status

Figure 28: Characteristics Mentioned by Different Settlement Types

Figure 29: Characteristics Mentioned by Different Genders

C Appendix C

All of the datasets that were used to quantify wild places were open-source and offered detailed information about aspects of the UK. Specifically, the datasets that we chose to use were as follows:

The 2020 Land Cover Classification Gridded Maps (Version 2.1.1) is an open-source dataset provided by Copernicus Climate Change Service. It offers global maps that depict the land surface in 22 distinct classes, as defined by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation's (UN FAO) Land Cover Classification System (LCCS)[]. The horizontal and vertical resolutions of the dataset are 300m and single level, respectively, with each pixel corresponding to a land cover class. The dataset is available in NetCDF4 format.

OS Terrain 50 is an open-source dataset of contours with spot heights, breaklines, coastline, lakes, ridges and formlines for Great Britain. The dataset is available in ESRI Shapefile (Contour) format.

The GloBio4 scenario (2015) offers spatial data on the overall mean species abundance (MSA), which integrates plants and warm-blooded vertebrates (birds and mammals) globally [12]. The dataset has a resolution of 10 arcseconds and is available in GeoTIFF format.

The OS Open Built Up Areas dataset provides information on the built-up areas of Great Britain. This dataset is available in both GeoPackage and CSV formats and contains polygons with attributes such as location names and area values, provided in units of square meters and hectares.

The LandScan Glob dataset provides estimates of the distribution of global population at a resolution of approximately 1KM. It is developed and maintained by the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL). This dataset employs a variety of data sources, including census data, satellite imagery, and other geographic information.

The Registered Charities data was obtained from UK government websites to show the level of community involvement in each county in Northern Ireland, England and Wales, and Scotland. The number of charities in each of these countries was sourced from their respective governing bodies - the Charity Commission or Northern Ireland, OSCR Scottish Charity Regulator, and Charity Commission for England and Wales.

Heritage lists were used to identify features of cultural importance. These lists includes designations of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONB), Battlefields (England), Battlefields (Scotland), Conservation areas (England and Wales), Gardens and designated landscapes (Scotland), GB Special Area of Conservation (SAC), GB Special Protection Areas (SPA), Historic Marine Protected Areas (Scotland), Historic Parks and Gardens (Wales), Local Nature Reserves, National Nature Reserves, National Scenic Areas (Scotland), National Trust Property, Parks and Gardens (England), RSPB Reserves, Scheduled Monuments (Scotland, England, and Wales), UK National Parks, UK RAMSAR sites, and World heritage sites.

The OS Roads dataset provides a comprehensive overview of the road network in Great Britain. The data is available in vector format, which includes nodes and links in the network. The links consist of roads that are classified by the National or Local Highway authority.

Outdoor recreation potential in Europe [13] provides the summary of the landscape's outdoor recreation potentials based on the preference and patterns of four tourist groups. The maps contain the potential values of a place that can be used for outdoor recreation. If the area shows higher potential for a group, it means the areas have more potential to conduct their preferred activities. While it also provides the preference of the outdoor activities for each tourist group, these can be regarded as a board image for the activity features. In particular, the tourist groups are convenience re-creationist, day tripper, education re-creationist, nature trekker and spiritual re-creationist. The convenience re-creationist would prefer easy short-term leisure activities and look for fire pits and picnic

sites. The day tripper would prefer active and sportive experiences and look for visitor centres. The education re-creationist is more interested in the heritages and rare ecosystems. The nature trekker is more attracted to “real nature” and adventure activities, such as “hiking, mountaineering and trekking”. This group will be more informative in identifying wildness. The spiritual re-creationist is looking for a connection with nature and beliefs.

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